

LINGUOCOGNITIVE ANALYSIS OF "FREEDOM" CONCEPT IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In recent years, attention has been paid to the cognitive analysis of language units in modern linguistics. The linguistic-cognitive analysis of the concept of "freedom" in the English and Uzbek national cultures opens up an opportunity to further study the cultures of these two nations. Contexts of use of the concept analyzed in this article and its synonymous meanings are explained on the basis of explanatory dictionaries.

Key words: Core lexeme, basic lexeme, concept, verbalization of concept, linguistic consciousness, T.G. Ardasheva, L.G. Popova, Y.S. Grishenko, N.M. Zhanpeisov, A.J. Jumakhanov.

In linguistics, the study of lexical units both within one language and several languages has been used for many years based on a cognitive approach. The tasks of this study, which aims to study the linguistic features of the concept of "freedom" in distantly related languages: English and Uzbek, are as follows:

- to determine the level of studying the verbalization of this concept in linguistics
- to determine and compare the composition of core lexemes that can express the meaning of this concept in English and Uzbek languages

According to explanatory dictionaries, the lexeme of freedom means the freedom to live your life as you wish, without interference from other people or authorities. Freedom is the freedom to go anywhere that you lose when you are incarcerated.¹

A.S. Solokhina in her candidate's thesis studies the manifestation of the concept of "free", "free" in English and Russian language cultures. He emphasizes that the essence of these concepts is the opposite relationship of freedom and freedom.² T. G. Ardasheva identifies the ethnic specificity of the concept of "freedom" in the candidate's thesis devoted to the linguistic-cognitive analysis of the Russian, English and French language materials. The researcher comes to the conclusion that the concept of "freedom" is the main concept that shapes the worldview of an individual and society, regulates the behavior of individuals in society, and has a wide scope of application.³ Moreover, comparative linguistics studies not only the concept of "free", but also the concept of "freedom" on the basis of related languages. V. D. Chekanova compares the German and Russian languages and identifies the specific

¹ Шаталова Т. И. Англо-русский идеографический словарь. М.: Рус. яз., 1994. 26-бет

² Солохина А. С. Концепт «свобода» в английской и русской лингвокультурах: дисс. ... к. филол. н. Волгоград, 2004. 191 с

³ Ардашева Т. Г. Лингвокогнитивный анализ концепта «свобода»: на материале русского, английского и французского языков: дисс. ... к. филол. н. Ижевск, 2012. 210 с.

features of the reflection of the concept of freedom in the linguistic consciousness of the speakers of these languages.⁴

When comparing unrelated languages, it is noted that there are linguistic works in which this concept is studied. In materials of English, Russian and Kazakh languages, this concept is studied by N. M. Zhanpeisov, A. J. Jumakhanov in connection with philosophical and everyday consciousness. Linguists came to the conclusion that the concept of "free" is a relevant concept in the "borderline" situations of transition from freedom to lack of freedom, both in the Kazakh language and in Russian and English.⁵ The presented analyzes showed the high relevance of the study of the verbalization of the concept.

However, in modern linguistics, the issue of expressing the concept of "freedom" through core lexemes is still not fully understood. Therefore, the novelty of the proposed work is, on the one hand, in revealing the methodology of determining the content of core lexemes that can express the concept, and on the other hand, in conducting a lexical-semantic comparative analysis of this concept in distantly related languages. To clarify the content of core lexemes, S.V. We turned to the method of reversibility proposed by Grinev-Grinevich and E. A. Sorokina.⁶ Its essence is to refer to bilingual dictionaries, which contain a lot of information about the semantic relations of the lexical systems of different languages. The use of the reverse method involves the division into several stages called "steps" and "turns", where "step" means the translation of the studied concept from the source language to another language, and "turn" - the next return (to the source language). Therefore, at the first stage, we turned to the information of the Russian-English dictionary, studied the English words expressing the concept of freedom.

Liberty is a right to freedom defined by law, such as freedom of speech. It also means doing something that could hurt or offend someone without asking permission. To be free means to have the right or permission to do something officially, to have freedom: a) to make unjustified changes to something; b) to treat someone with disrespect, to be too quick, too friendly. A person who lives in freedom is free from the repressive restrictions imposed by the government on his way of life, behavior or political views in society and the state. The Statue of Liberty in the USA is an example of this. The power or scope of action that people can enjoy the freedom to act and express their desires is called freedom.⁷

Another core lexeme expressing the concept of freedom in the English language is the lexeme "liberty". Let us turn to his interpretations in explanatory and bilingual dictionaries of the English language. As a result, we witness the following comments:

1. The status of a person who is free, not imprisoned or enslaved. Certain restrictions or no restrictions at all; free, unconditional state.⁸

⁴ Чеканова В. Д. Концепт «Свобода» в немецком и русском языках [Электронный ресурс]. URL: http://www.rusnauka.com/12_KPSN_2013/Philologia/7_135358.doc.htm (дата обращения: 13.09.2018).

⁵ Жанпеисова Н. М., Жумаханова А. Ж. Концепт СВОБОДА в английской, русской и казахской лингвокультурах [Электронный ресурс] // Наука вчера, сегодня, завтра: сб. ст. по материалам XIII Международной научно-практической конференции. Новосибирск: СибАК, 2014. № 6 (13). URL: <https://sibac.info/conf/science/xiii/38538> (дата обращения: 13.09.2017).

⁶ Щепотина Е. В. Экспериментальное исследование концептов freedom, law, свобода, закон в английской и русской лингвокультурах // Филологические науки в России и за рубежом: материалы III Международной научной конференции (г. Санкт-Петербург, июль 2015 г.). СПб.: Свое издательство, 2015. С. 117-120.

⁷ <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/liberty> (дата обращения: 13.09.2018).

⁸ Английский толковый словарь [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <http://engood.ru/anglijskij-tolkovyy-slovar/> (дата обращения: 13.11.2018).

2. Honorary citizen with certain privileges; independence; right; directness, openness, mobility; relief, privilege; freedom⁹

Popova L.G., Grishenko Y.S. In the article "Kotseptualnoe ponimanie svobody v angliyskom i russkom yazykax" they found out the following common and specific features when comparing the semantics of core lexemes expressing the concept of "freedom" in English and Russian languages. General concept of freedom

- the ability to go anywhere, which you lose when you are in prison;
- the right granted by law;
- will, freedoms.

The peculiarity of the understanding of freedom in English is the expression of freedom

- the freedom to live your life as you want, without the interference of other people or authorities, without asking for permission that might offend or hurt someone;

- Statue of Liberty in the USA;
- liberation of a person from the control of fate;
- a sea trip given to a sailor;
- arrogant speech or action;
- honorary citizenship;
- directness, openness;
- mobility, lightness;
- comfort;
- privilege;

In Russian, the core lexeme "svoboda" with its semantics expresses such a unique concept.

- no limitation, lack of limitation in something;
- not deprived of the opportunity to act according to his will;
- certain, limited, well-known work-related actions or the range of its different levels;
- unemployment;

The Merriam-Webster annotated dictionary defines the word "liberty" as follows:

• "the power, right, or opportunity to choose" Freedom of choice has the following synonyms:¹⁰ 1) choice - choice; 2) discretion - discretion; 3) alternative - alternative; 4) volition - will; 5) vote - voting; 6) pick - selection; 7) inclination - inclination; 8) partiality - partiality; 9) will - desire; 10) voice - voice; 11) proclivity - inclination; 12) predilection - inclination; 13) penchant - inclination; 14) propensity; 15) judgment - verdict; 16) option - choice; 17) preference - preference; 18) way - road; 19) election - election; 20) selection - selection; 21) liking - liking; 22) determination - persistence; 23) free will - free will; 24) druthers - druther; 25) say - say; 26) perspicacity - intelligibility; 27) tendency - desire; 28) judgment - verdict; 29) discernment - intelligence.

⁹ [http://www.diclib.com/cgi-](http://www.diclib.com/cgi-bin/d.cgi?p=liberty&page=search&l=ru&base=&prefbase=&newinput=1&st=&diff_examples=1&category=cat3#.XHVa9pYqzpc)

[bin/d.cgi?p=liberty&page=search&l=ru&base=&prefbase=&newinput=1&st=&diff_examples=1&category=cat3#.XHVa9pYqzpc](http://www.diclib.com/cgi-bin/d.cgi?p=liberty&page=search&l=ru&base=&prefbase=&newinput=1&st=&diff_examples=1&category=cat3#.XHVa9pYqzpc) (дата обращения: 13.11.2018).

¹⁰ [https://www.merriam-](https://www.merriam-webster.com/thesaurus/liberty#:~:text=The%20words%20freedom%20and%20license%20are%20common%20synonyms%20of%20liberty)

[webster.com/thesaurus/liberty#:~:text=The%20words%20freedom%20and%20license%20are%20common%20synonyms%20of%20liberty](https://www.merriam-webster.com/thesaurus/liberty#:~:text=The%20words%20freedom%20and%20license%20are%20common%20synonyms%20of%20liberty)

The following lexemes are considered contrary to the concept of "liberty": 1) force - power; 2) duty - duty; 3) duress - coercion; 4) coercion - forcing; 5) obligation - obligation; 6) Hobson's choice - duty, obligation

- "autonomy; the state of being free from the control or power of another" (autonomy; the state of being free from the power or control of the other party).¹¹ In this sense, it has the following synonyms: 1) sovereignty - sovereignty; 2) independence - independence; 3) emancipation - freedom; 4) self-determination - self-determination; 5) self-government - self-management; 6) enfranchisement; 7) freedom - freedom; 8) independence - independence; 9) liberation - freedom; 10) self-governance - self-management; 11) sovereignty; 12) manumission; 13) release - freedom;

The lexemes that contradict the concept of "autonomy" are the following; 1) dependence; 2) heteronomy-dependence; 3) subjection; 4) unfreedom-lack of freedom; 5) subjugation.

The words "Freedom" and "license" are common synonyms of the lexeme "liberty". Although all three words mean "the power or condition of acting without coercion," the concept of "liberty" is more closely related to the meaning of freedom achieved after previous restraint or coercion.

The released prisoner had difficulty adjusting to his new freedom
(The released prisoner struggled to adjust to his new freedom)

In some situations, the lexeme "freedom" can be used instead of the word "liberty". However, the concept of "freedom" has a comprehensive meaning and means freedom from the influence of coercion and demands.

Freedom of press¹²

¹¹ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/thesaurus/liberty#:~:text=The%20words%20freedom%20and%20license%20are%20common%20synonyms%20of%20liberty>

¹² <https://www.merriam-webster.com/thesaurus/liberty#:~:text=The%20words%20freedom%20and%20license%20are%20common%20synonyms%20of%20liberty>

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